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On the way to higher education: Reflections on the importance of work-place conditions and the team to promote educational pathways

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Abstract

Vocational education and training helps young people to quickly and effectively enter the labour market. To advance their careers and to develop their professional expertise, even more, they must then further their education through higher vocational or higher academic education. In a recent study, we found distinct predictors for those engaged in higher academic education than for those engaged in higher vocational education. Whereas higher academic education is predicted by high social status, no migration background and a high value of further education, engagement in higher vocational education is predicted by high learning opportunities at work, low social support and a high value of further education. In reflecting these findings, it is discussed what factors help to turn a workplace into a learning place: can a reflection on factors that What makes a workplace a learning place: organisational norms and values, workplace conditions and the team / the colleagues.

Keywords

workplace learning; learning culture; higher vocational education; job design; team

1 Introduction

Vocational education and training (VET) helps young people to quickly and effectively enter the labour market if knowledge and skills acquired are in line with the demands of the companies and industries. In VET, students follow a job-specific, specialised training and specialise earlier than students in academic education. This early specialisation gets the students more easily into jobs as it raises their employability, but it can also lead to reduced adaptability to changing occupational environments later (Hampf & Woessmann, 2016). Further education after initial VET is therefore important, as this helps an individual not only to advance his or her career but also to sustain and develop the knowledge and skills needed for innovation and sustainability in a changing and competitive labour market.

Engagement in further education during a person's early professional career depends on a multitude of factors and not all individuals pursue further education after having graduated from initial VET. The literature on workplace learning sees structures, norms, values and practices in the workplace as key factors to motivate and engage employees in learning activities (Billett, 2014). As most learning at the workplace is informal and incidental, individual and social factors also become important, as there is a constant need to identify learning-situations and to make use of them (Nägele & Stalder, 2019). Learning at work is often very similar to a problem-solving process as the learner needs to frame the context, react to situational triggers, produce alternative solutions, assess intended and unintended consequences, and he or she needs to evaluate what has been done and learnt in accordance with the co-workers (Watkins & Marsick, 1992).

In this paper, results from an empirical study are summarised in which we looked at the pathways to higher education in a sample of young adults after having finished their initial education and training (Nägele, Neuenschwander, & Rodcharoen, 2018). The result of this study urges us to reflect on the role of work and relations at work to advance individual educational careers. If learning opportunities at work are an essential factor for becoming engaged in higher professional education, then we need to talk about measures to foster incidental and informal learning and the role of non-formal learning at the workplace as means to advance educational careers (Nägele & Stalder, 2019).

2 Becoming engaged in higher education¹

An individual's desire to move towards higher education develops on the one hand out of learning activities at work. On the other hand, social status factors can trigger an individual's engagement towards higher education. Learning opportunities, social support and sociodemographic factors are often discussed in the literature as primary drivers of becoming engaged in higher education. Furthermore, an individual will only invest in further education if it attributes some value to the further education (Nägele et al., 2018).

Perception of learning opportunities. Work offers incidental, informal, non-formal, or formal learning opportunities as interacting modes of learning (La Belle, 1982). An individual's perception of learning opportunities at work is a prerequisite to develop the knowledge, skills and attitudes needed and to develop future perspectives concerning their competence development and educational plans (Janssens, Smet, Onghena, & Kyndt, 2017; Kraiger, Ford, & Salas, 1993).

Social support. Social support, on the one hand, helps individuals to achieve self-imposed career goals and can foster career aspirations and development (Hofmann, Stalder, Tschan, & Häfeli, 2014). On the other hand, teams can develop internal performance norms or an unwillingness to change the composition and role distribution, imposing pressure on a team member that wants to change the team structure by, e.g. attending further education. Thus, social support can either be a valuable resource that helps individuals to cope with workplace affordances or a team can also hinder learning and development by imposing internal group norms on an individual.

Sociodemographic factors. The social origin of an individual, as represented by the family's socioeconomic status, was found to be one of the significant explanatory variables of educational pathways (Becker, 2016; Lamamra, 2017). Social origin affects the transition from school to education as well as the transition to higher education (Swiss Coordination Centre for Research in Education [SKBF CSRE], 2014). For individuals with migrant backgrounds, it is harder to access higher education. A significant effect of migration status is found in the transition to upper-secondary education and in the transition to tertiary education (Hupka-Brunner, Sacchi, & Stalder, 2010; Picot & Hou, 2013). *Gender* stereotypes and gendered career expectations result in very persistent gender differences and inequalities in the Swiss labour market (Hadjar & Aeschlimann, 2014).

Value of further education. Motivational theories on career choices and planning propose that educational values (attainment, interest, utility) and expectations predict educational

¹ Based on: Nägele, C., Neuenschwander, M. P., & Rodcharoen, P. (2018). Higher education in Switzerland: Predictors of becoming engaged in higher vocational or academic education – the role of workplace factors. *International Journal for Research in Vocational Education and Training*, 5(4), 264–284. <https://doi.org/10.13152/IJRVET.5.4.2>

choices (Wigfield, Rosenzweig, & Eccles, 2017). Values represent the relative importance given to a specific educational choice, and if a person does not attribute high value to higher education, little chance exists that this option will be chosen (Brown & Crace, 1996).

2.1 Higher education in Switzerland

The study was run in the Switzerland where tertiary education features a two-tier structure with higher vocational education (also called *professional education*) and higher academic education (*university-based education*). On the upper secondary level, most young people follow the vocational track (78% in 2016 according to figures of the Federal Statistical Office). After having finished initial VET, graduates can mainly follow three pathways: 1) They can work, 2) they can attend higher vocational education, or 3) they can attend higher academic education on the condition of having baccalaureate degrees (Stalder & Nägele, 2011). Higher vocational and higher academic education are both seen as equal in value on the same ISCED level.

2.2 Sample

Data stem from a multi-cohort longitudinal questionnaire-based survey study with three waves on educational decisions and educational pathways (BEN), running from 2012 to 2016 in the German part of Switzerland (Neuenschwander & Düggele, 2013). Individuals were selected for the analyses in this paper only if they had not acquired diplomas in higher vocational or higher academic education before 2014. The final sample consisted of 601 individuals. Multinomial regression models were run, using SPSS 25 (IBM Corp., 2017).

2.3 Results

The results revealed two distinct sets of predictor variables for higher vocational education and higher academic education. High opportunities to learn at the workplace and low social support predicted engagement in higher vocational education, whereas social origin and nationality predicted engagement in higher academic education. Gender had no effect at all. The value attributed to further higher education was predictive for both higher vocational education and higher academic education. This study shows not only two distinct patterns for the engagement in higher vocational or higher academic education, but it also adds further evidence that workplace factors play a crucial role in the development of knowledge, skills and attitudes and the engagement in further education (Nägele et al., 2018).

3 Reflections on the importance of workplace conditions and the team to promote educational pathways²

In the study presented above, a critical variable that triggers higher vocational education is the perception of the workplace as a learning place. The question is: What makes a workplace a learning place? The short answer is: organisational norms and values, workplace conditions and the team / the colleagues.

Learning in the workplace is contextualised learning, embedded in the work process. Learning can be informal and incidental or non-formal (learning events organised by an or-

² For an in-depth discussion see Nägele, C., & Stalder, B. E. (2019). Motivation and engagement of learners in organizations. In S. McGrath, M. Mulder, J. Papier, & R. Stuart (Eds.), *Handbook of vocational education and training: Developments in the changing world of work*. Springer.

ganisation). Informal learning situations can occur at any time during work, for example when a problem arises, when reflecting individually or in the group about how to do the job or a specific task, before, during or after having finished the task. It is then a decision of the individual and the team to switch from a "production-mode" to a "learning mode". Factors that facilitate this mode-switching lay in organisational social structures and norms, the job design, the work team including the opportunities to network and interact with more experienced colleagues, tutors, supervisors, and mentors (Kyndt, Govaerts, Smet, & Dochy, 2018). Organisational structures, norms, values and more specifically the organisational learning culture are communicated through organisational socialisation processes. These processes are essential as they inform an individual the expectations regarding the development of knowledge, skills and attitudes (Saks & Gruman, 2012). Job design which is about how work is structured, organised, experienced, and enacted (Grant, Fried, Parker, & Frese, 2010) is a critical factor in enabling learning at work. A job design favourable for learning incorporates factors as for example the possibility to cooperate, to evaluate the own work and to get and give feedback, have opportunities to reflect individually or in the team, to gather and share information, to give and receive guidance, and to have appropriate job demands and job control (Janssens et al., 2017). The core job dimensions most often discussed are skill variety, task identity, task significance, autonomy, and feedback (Oldham & Hackman, 2010). The task must be complex and demanding with respect to knowledge and skills as well as information processing needs, as boredom and underuse of skills does not motivate at all to invest in job-related learning. A well-designed job allows an individual to select own goals, to self-regulate its learning, and shape its learning pathway (Kanfer, Frese, & Johnson, 2017). Supervisors and teams are crucial by making it possible to learn, explore ideas and processes, to discuss differences, and resolve these differences with the aim to co-construct a new and shared understanding of the situation (Lehmann-Willenbrock, 2017). The availability and willingness of trainers, co-workers, and supervisors to share information and provide precise, constructive, and helpful feedback and to offer adequate guidance and support are therefore essential for learning (Kyndt, Vermeire, & Cabus, 2016). The development of teams, learning in teams and team learning are complex processes shaped by social and temporal processes (Lehmann-Willenbrock, 2017). But still, not all processes are understood. But generally, a positive team learning culture relying on shared perceptions usually foster learning in teams (Gil & Mataveli, 2017). Indeed, individual factors such as personality, attitudes towards learning, proactivity, self-efficacy and self-awareness about the situation will influence the perception of a workplace as a learning place. But we need to be aware, that these factors are shaped by workplace factors (Schallberger, Häfeli, & Kraft, 1984).

To foster the perception of a workplace as a learning place and to support informal learning, it is best to start by reflecting and transmitting organisational norms through organisational socialisation, to optimise the job design and to have a closer look at the team processes. This will help an individual to perceive a workplace as a learning place.

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